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Navigating the Social Landscape through Friendship Formation in the Senior High School

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Abstract

The study "Navigating the Social Landscape through Friendship Formation in Senior High School" focuses on forming friendships among Senior High School Students at Artacho National High School. The research used a mixed-methods approach, using a floating questionnaire and random interviews. With 111 respondents in the Quantitative Part and 20 respondents who underwent the interview with 3 sessions, the findings revealed that interests, hobbies, personality, gender, and social support influence friendship formation, with cultural, socioeconomic, and psychological aspects also playing a role. Social media and technology also impact friendship formation, with the latter affecting the expansion of social networks, trust, authenticity, misunderstandings, shared hobbies, and maintaining existing friendships. The study concludes that certain factors, such as social media and technology, influence friendship formation among senior high school students.

Keywords: *social landscape, friendship formation, socialization*

Introduction

Friendship is a bond between two or more individuals who care about each other and enjoy spending time together (James, 2024). It is based on trust, mutual respect, and support and can involve various activities and experiences (Huff, 2022). Friendship development factors include similarity, personality, gender, cultural variations, social support, and emotional needs. In Europe, adolescents from the iGeneration often feel lonely, and a proactive strategy to encourage close friendships as part of social-emotional learning (SEL) is suggested.

In a secure and wealthy community, friendship is highly valued, but people often value those who share their social beliefs. In a multicultural society, individuals engage at work, on the job, or in school to share these values (Tarika, 2021). School attendance positively impacts relational inclusion and widens friendship circles, even in highly segregated accommodation structures like refugee hospitals (Al-Hroub, 2021).

Peers and friends are a significant resource, particularly when switching from primary to secondary school (Peer Pressure, 2024). However, no original theories regarding friendship development exist or how to incorporate early adolescents into studies. Factors like homophily and self-disclosure contribute to friendship formation among mainstream groups, but additional challenges face members of diverse groups and racial and ethnic minorities (Thomas, 2019).

In the American context, peer impact on adolescents is well documented, but little is known about the factors that affect how each person is susceptible to influence (Laursen & Veenstra, 2021). Closest friendships between people of the same sex are most likely to develop in environments encouraging regular in-person interactions between people from similar social groups and backgrounds.

Understanding social dynamics in pre-and early teenage years can help understand how friends' likeability and popularity influence their interactions and relationships (Laursen et al., 2023), as popularity may reflect social skills and position, while likeability reflects personal traits. Higher levels of relational aggression, prosocial behavior, and academic achievement among partners who are more liked predict more significant rises in the same among couples who are less liked but not the other way around (Parker, 2018). Physical violence among mates who are disliked predicted increases in physical aggression among partners who are wanted. More popular friends unexpectedly influenced the academic achievement of less popular friends, but less popular friends did not affect any of these variables.

In Asia, a second-year Korean middle school conducted an inquiry science experiment class, finding that the inquiry experiment class had higher tie density, an average of friends, and connections. The study also found that the inquiry experiment class was more effective in promoting member ratings and creating a fully attached friendship (Kim, 2023).

In China, the academic performance of regular students is significantly negatively impacted by the proportion of low-ability students in a class. The study demonstrates that as students approach middle school, their social networks and learning environment change, which causes disparities in peer effects of low-ability students (Chen et al., 2023).

In Indonesia, friendship quality is still unclear, but studies have shown a direct correlation between the quality of friendship and various adaptive abilities, academic success, and school performance. Peers and friends are mental health and well-being resources, especially during primary and secondary school transitions (Alsarrani et al., 2022). Furthermore, the study also found that peer pressure and academic achievement are related to peers affecting students' performance in activities. The findings suggest that peer pressure and students' academic achievement are related.

In the local context, students and teachers have expressed concerns about the lack of bonding between students and unity. Factors such as culture, race, and life status also impact friendship formation, with some students choosing to isolate rather than make friends due to differences in culture, beliefs, and race.

The study aims to offer a significant understanding of the dynamics of social relationships and student-to-student interactions. As well as spot potential roadblocks or opportunities to fortify friendships. To navigate the social landscape of the Senior High School of Artacho National High School through friendship formation, the following research questions were formulated to gather the data needed for the study. First, what are the key factors that influence the respondents' friendship regarding Interests and Hobbies, Social Support, and Emotional Needs? Second, what is the extent of friendship formation impact in terms of socio-economic factors and individual perception? Lastly, what are the effects of social media on friendship formation?

Literature Review

Friendship Formation among the Youth Today

Alsarrani et al. (2022) conducted a comprehensive review to evaluate the relationship between friendship quality and teenagers' mental wellness. According to the study, social integration with friends significantly impacts adolescents' conduct and well-being. The quality of friendships can either help or hinder mental development during adolescence¹. The review indicates the importance of developing healthy friendships in adolescents' subjective well-being.

Another study conducted by Pouwels et al. (2021) investigated the impact of social media use on relationship closeness in adolescents' daily lives. The study revealed favorable inter-person connections between friendship closeness and overall WhatsApp and Instagram use among close friends. However, at the within-person level, small negative correlations were found between general WhatsApp and Instagram use (with and without close friends) and closeness to friendship. These findings highlight the need for person-specific effects in developmental and media effect theories.

The studies above emphasize the importance of friendship quality, social media use, and social perspective-taking in developing friendships and the social landscape among young people. However, all of the studies on friendship-building found positive short-term results but equivocal long-term impacts (Manchanda et al., 2023). While friendship therapies can have immediate favorable effects, their long-term efficacy remains unknown. However, further research is required to comprehend these intricate relationships completely. It is also worth noting that these results may differ depending on the youth's cultural, social, and individual settings.

Methodology

The researchers used a Mixed Method approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methodologies to study social phenomena. Qualitative research involves systematic inquiry, while quantitative research involves analyzing numerical data. Quantitative research design focuses on descriptive research, providing precise descriptions of populations, situations, and phenomena.

The researchers employed a complete enumeration in the quantitative phase in which a custom-designed questionnaire with five indicators per domain was used to collect the data. The qualitative phase uses a snowball sampling technique to identify the 5 respondents from each strand for the interview, including 10 open-ended questions.

The School Head validated the research instrument, the Guidance Designate and one English Teacher while the reliability of the self-made questionnaire is at .08 using the Cronbach Alpha analysis which is interpreted as reliable.

The respondents are the Senior High School Students of Artacho National High School, comprising students from GAS, HUMSS, STEM, and ABM. Before commencing the distribution of questionnaires to the intended respondents, the researchers obtained consent from the school principal and the subject teachers to conduct interviews and administer the surveys.

To summarize the data from the key factors of friendship formation and the extent of friendship formation, the average weighted mean using a 4-point Likert Scale using the SPSS software. And to identify the themes using codes, the MAXQDA was used to code the effects of social media in friendship formation.

This study adheres to ethical norms, providing respondents with signed informed consent and communicating study objectives, information requirements, and willingness to participate. Confidentiality and anonymity are maintained, and participants' identities are not disclosed. Researchers treat respondents with respect and ensure their well-being. Data collected is meticulously documented, and respondents can withdraw from the study if they no longer wish to participate.

Results and Discussion

The table reveals that personality traits significantly influence students' everyday decisions, particularly in leisure activities and work tasks. This is particularly important for friendships, as shared traits can significantly influence the development of friendships. However, the lowest mean value of indicator 1 (2.71) suggests that trust is crucial in forming friendships. Trust plays a significant role in how friends react to new experiences or products, and if not accepted, individuals may feel excluded or excluded. Openness and trust can help friendships grow stronger, but improper handling can have a negative effect. Therefore, openness and trust are essential

for a rich exchange of experiences and ideas in friendships.

Table 1. Key factors that influence friendship formation among Senior High School students in terms of Interests and Hobbies (N=111)

<i>Interest and Hobbies</i>	SD	D	SA	A	WM	I
<i>Indicators</i>						
1. I appreciate it when my friends introduce me to new things.	10	34	46	21	2.70	A
2. I enjoy exploring new hobbies and activities.	5	5	66	35	3.18	A
3. I enjoy participating in group activities and showing common interest.	4	8	57	42	3.23	A
4. I believe having shared interests is essential for building lasting friendships.	3	7	70	31	3.16	A
5. I respect and support my friends' interests and times, even if they differ from mine	3	8	63	37	3.21	A
Overall Mean					3.07	A

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76 – 2.50 D (Disagree), 2.51 – 3.3.25 A (Agree), and 3.26 – 4.00 SA (Strongly Agree)

Table 2. Key factors that influence friendship formation among senior high school students in terms of Social Support and Emotional Needs (N=111)

<i>Social Support and Emotional Needs</i>	SD	D	SA	A	WM	I
<i>Indicators</i>						
1. I made friends with the student who advised me on my problem.	7	8	56	40	3.16	A
2. I prefer to make friends with my fellow students.	5	6	63	37	3.19	A
3. I prefer to make friends with older or more mature.	6	6	69	23	3.12	A
4. I prefer to have friends who seem to have more life experience.	5	9	74	23	3.04	A
5. I prefer to have friends with different age groups.	6	7	61	37	3.16	A
Total					3.13	A

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76 – 2.50 D (Disagree), 2.51 – 3.3.25 A (Agree), and 3.26 – 4.00 SA (Strongly Agree)

In Table 2, it was found that students prefer making friends with their peers, as it leads to cooperative learning and intellectual ideas sharing, improving knowledge and GPAs, as reflected in the highest mean of 3.19 under indicator 2. This is similar to the study by Alotaibi et al. (2023), which states that students prefer to form friendships with their peers, believing it leads to cooperative learning. Conversely, students prefer friends with more life experiences, as they value guidance and find it essential. This suggests that not all friends have the same life experiences, as not all future friends will have the same experiences.

However, the lowest mean is 3.04 in question variable 4, suggesting that not all friends have the same life experiences. The study of Shanti et al. (2021) emphasizes the importance of developing social support and emotional needs for friendship, as students desire someone who supports them the same way they do when studying.

Table 3. Extent of friendship formation impact in terms of Socio-economic (N=111)

<i>Socio-economic</i>	SD	D	SA	A	WM	I
<i>Indicators</i>						
1. Friendship may indicate inequality and promote fairness	4	11	60	36	3.15	A
2. Friendship may help with financial issues	3	14	73	21	3.01	A
3. Friendship may establish good communication among learners.	3	24	70	14	2.86	A
4. Friendships bridge the gaps between the less fortunate and rich ones.	3	6	78	24	3.11	A
5. Friendship eliminates discrimination in the state of students' lives.	5	19	73	14	2.86	A
Total					3.00	A

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76 – 2.50 D (Disagree), 2.51 – 3.3.25 A (Agree), and 3.26 – 4.00 SA (Strongly Agree)

Table 3 shows that friendship can promote fairness and inequality, as it can be established regardless of a student's financial status. Genuine friendships thrive on a person's identity, not their financial status. Low-income students are less likely to be chosen as friends and establish friendships, suggesting that fostering acceptance and sincerity can improve social integration and foster friendships.

Table 4. Extent of friendship formation impact in terms of Individual Perception (N=111)

<i>Individual Perception</i>	SD	D	SA	A	WM	I
<i>Indicators</i>						
1. Friendship boosts confidence and self-esteem.	5	4	59	43	3.26	A
2. Friendship offers an opportunity to become more open and communicate.	6	4	63	38	3.20	A
3. Friendship can make a learner feel loved and connected.	5	5	57	44	3.26	A
4. Friendship is offered to a student.	2	7	66	36	3.23	A
5. Friendship may protect learners against mental health issues such as depression and anxiety.	8	5	64	34	3.12	A
Total					3.21	A

Legend: 1.00 – 1.75 Strongly Disagree (SD), 1.76 – 2.50 D (Disagree), 2.51 – 3.3.25 A (Agree), and 3.26 – 4.00 SA (Strongly Agree)

The table 4 reveals that friendships can significantly boost students' confidence and self-esteem. Gaining confidence is a gradual process

that requires learning from experiences and collaborating with supportive friends. As John Donne's quote, "No man is an island," suggests, friendships can also make a learner feel loved and connected.

On the other hand, friendships can help individuals cope with mental health issues like anxiety and depression by providing emotional support. Research has shown that having joyful friends is more likely to help individuals recover from depression (Tara et al., 2023). Additionally, hanging out with friends can reduce stress, as simple conversations can help reduce stress (Arlin Cuncic, 2023). Friendships are crucial in enhancing students' confidence, self-awareness, and well-being.

Themes	Word Count	Percentage
1. Expanded social networks	7,345	27%
2. Trust and Authenticity	6,895	26%
3. Misunderstanding and Miscommunication	4,287	16%
4. Shared interests and Hobbies	4,112	15%
5. Maintaining existing friendship	4,103	15%

Figure 1. Thematic analysis of the effect of social media on friendship formation

The researchers identified Expanded Social Networks as the first theme in their analysis of the impact of social media on friendship formation, with a word count of 7,345 and a 27% percentage. This was reflected in the answer by Julia (not her real name) "*Ginagamit ko po siya like may mga bago pong salita or mga words na nae-encounter ko uhhh sa mga sinasabi po ng mga teachers, ginagamit ko po 'yung social media sa pagse-search po ng mga new things uhhh sa pakikipag-communicate rin po sa mga friends ko na nandito lang po sa'min or malapit sa school*" to the question *Maaari mo bang ilarawan nang maikli kung paano mo ginagamit ang social media at teknolohiya sa iyong pang-araw-araw na buhay? lalong nalo na ang social media?*"

The second theme based on the results of the thematic analysis on the effect of social media on friendship formation is trust and authenticity. Where the word count is 6,895, and the percentage is 26%. As to the interview question like "*Sa palagay mo, naiimpluwensyahan ba ng social media ang paraan ng pagpapakita ng mga tao sa kanilang sarili kapag sinusubukang magkaroon ng mga bagong kaibigan?*" the respondents answered "*Para po sa'kin, oo, kasi kung ano yung nakikita nila sa social media just for example yung image niya sa social media is maganda, parang kung makikipag-kaibigan sila sa ibang tao ang pinapakita nila is kung ano lang yung image nila sa social media.*"

The effect of social media on friendship formation through thematic analysis is based on misunderstanding and miscommunication in social media, where the researchers found out that the count words words is 4,287, and the percentage is 16%. This reflects on the question on "*What challenges, if any, do you see in forming and maintaining friendships through social media and technology*" got two respondent and, girly one respondent answered the question "*Mayroon ka bang anumang mga alalahanin tungkol sa epekto ng teknolohiya sa pagiging tunay ng pagkakaibigan.*" (*Miss P: Uhhh, yung mga hamon maaaring pagba bakstaban ganun or kaya hindi totoo yung kausap mo sa kung hindi siya yung, hindi niya totoong identity yun yun yung isa sa mga hamon na nasa isip ko. One of the challenges is that there might be deception or the person you're talking to may not have a genuine identity. That's one of the challenges that comes to mind.*)

Also, the researchers found that maintaining existing Friendships is the result of the analysis of the effect of social media on friendship formation, which has a 4,103-word count and a percentage of 15%.

Conclusion

Overall, the study has yielded valuable insights between the quality of friendships and individuals' personalities. First, personality traits influence students' decisions, especially in leisure and work tasks. Second, friendship fosters cooperative learning, intellectual sharing, knowledge improvement, fairness, and self-esteem, regardless of financial status, and can promote fairness and inequality. Lastly, friendship formation using social media has a dualistic nature which has both positive and negative effects on friendship formation. On one hand, it allows for connecting with old friends and making new ones across geographical boundaries. On the other hand, it can lead to shallow interactions and a decrease in face-to-face communication.

Moreover, the results emphasize the significance of considering personality dynamics in friendships, as they can significantly impact the quality of interactions and the overall satisfaction obtained from these connections as reflected in the connection between the numerical data and the interview result from the respondents.

Based on the conclusions drawn, it is recommended that educational institutions and social platforms consider the significant role of personality traits in influencing student decisions. Tailored programs could be developed to help students understand their traits and make informed decisions in both leisure and work tasks.

Furthermore, it's also important to stress the value of friendship in promoting self-esteem, justice, intellectual sharing, cooperative learning, and knowledge advancement. In order to foster a sense of equality among students, schools should establish settings that support the development of friendships among all students, regardless of their financial situation.

Also, even though social media has helped people make friends beyond geographic borders, its dualistic character needs to be addressed. It can result in superficial connections and a decline in in-person communication. Social media companies should think of creative ways to promote deeper conversations and balance virtual and in-person networking. This might lessen the detrimental effects of social media on the development of friendships.

Lastly, further research is needed to fully understand the long-term impact of social media on friendship formation..

References

- Al-Hroub, A. (2021). The Impact of Inclusion on the Performance of Students with and without special education needs. [https://www.academia.edu/44017578/](https://www.academia.edu/44017578/The_Impact_of_Inclusion_on_the_Performance_of_Students_with_and_without_special_education_needs) The Impact of Inclusion on the Performance of Students with and without special education needs.
- Alsarrani, A., Hunter, R. F., Dunne, L., & Garcia, L. M. T. (2022). Association between friendship quality and subjective well-being among adolescents: a systematic review. *BMC Public Health*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-14776-4>
- APA PsycNet. (n.d.). <https://psycnet.apa.org/fulltext/2021-14131-010.html>
- Blaskova, L. J., & Gibson, J. L. (2024). Exploring concepts of friendship formation in children with language disorder using a qualitative framework analysis. *International Journal of Language and Communication Disorders*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1460-6984.13021>
- Dresler-Hawke, E., Geyang, Z., & Vaccarino, F. (2014). The Perception of friendship Formation: A comparative study of New Zealand and China tertiary students. *The International Journal of Learner Diversity and Identities*, 20(4), 29–41. <https://doi.org/10.18848/2327-0128/cgp/v20i04/48586>
- Faur, S., & Laursen, B. (2022). Classroom seat proximity predicts friendship formation. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.796002>
- Gerodias, D. F. (2023). A focus on the contextualized learning activity sheets. <https://ejournals.ph/article.php?id=19406>
- Kastner, M. (2022). Formation and Benefits of Intercultural friendships: The Role of communication. *Journal of Intercultural Communication*, 21(3), 26–40. <https://doi.org/10.36923/jicc.v21i3.19>
- Laursen, B., & Veenstra, R. (2021). Toward understanding the functions of peer influence: A summary and synthesis of recent empirical research. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 31(4), 889–907. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jora.12606>
- Laursen, B., Leggett-James, M. P., & Valdes, O. (2023). Relative likeability and relative popularity as sources of influence in children's friendships. *PloS One*, 18(5), e0283117. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0283117>
- Manchanda, T., Stein, A., & Fazel, M. (2023). Investigating the Role of friendship interventions on the mental health outcomes of Adolescents: A scoping review of the range and a Systematic Review of Effectiveness. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(3), 2160. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20032160>
- Mather-Pike, C. E. M.-P. (2018). A participatory action research project to improve school readiness in rural Grade R classes in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. *Core*. <https://core.ac.uk/download/288925937.pdf>
- Pouwels, J. L., Valkenburg, P. M., Beyens, I., Van Driel, I. I., & Keijsers, L. (2021). Social media use and friendship closeness in adolescents' daily lives: An experience sampling study. *Developmental Psychology*, 57(2), 309–323. <https://doi.org/10.1037/dev0001148>
- Tarika, D. (2021, June 29). Working in a multi-cultural environment. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/working-multi-cultural-environment-dirgha-tarika/>
- Thomas, R. J. (2019). Sources of Friendship and Structurally Induced Homophily across the Life Course. *Sociological Perspectives*, 62(6), 822–843. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0731121419828399>
- Wicaksono, B., & Adiyanti, M. G. (2019). Understanding the dynamics of friendship formation among high school adolescent: Indigenous psychology approach. *Psychological Research and Intervention*, 2(1), 28–35. <https://doi.org/10.21831/pri.v2i1.28048>

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